

7. An Analytical study on Financial Distress Level of Automobile Industries in India

Dr. Kandarp Chavda

Adhyapak Sahayak, S. L. U. Arts and H. & P. Thakore Commerce College for Women, Ellisbridge, Ahmedabad.

Mr. Vaibhav Gallani

Assistant Professor, Shri K. K. Shastri Government Commerce College, Maninagar (E), Ahmedabad.

Abstract

The number of elucidative evaluation tools are gradually increasing in the market day by day and due to the availability of lots of sources, an investor is being strengthened by having a rich data analysis of particular investment alternative. In this digital era, there are many tools and techniques have been emerged in the field of accounting also such as forensic accounting. The Altman Z score model is one of the most popular methods of forensic accounting which is widely used to predict the company's financial distress level. The model offers a more favoured way to analyse the organization's financial health than any other method. In this research paper, an attempt has been made to evaluate a financial health of selected companies of automobile industries by using the Altman Z Score model. In order to evaluate fair, ten-years period from 2014 to 2023 has been selected for the research.

Key Words: Financial Distress, Altman Z score model, Performance Evaluation, automobile companies, Zone.

Introduction

Since last few decades, the number of investors is increasing in terms of investment into securities and funds. With the increasing interest of investment, the investors are also required to measure the performance of the companies with the modern techniques. As investment into securities and funds are risky, the investors must try to secure the future of the investment by evaluating the necessary facts and figures of the company in which they are interested to invest their money. According to one survey, India has the fourth biggest automobile sector in the world, and it is now the seventh and fourth largest vehicle maker globally. of trucks used for business purposes in 2018. By 2026, the Indian automotive sector—which includes component

manufacturing—is projected to generate between Rs 16.16 and Rs 18.18 trillion (US\$ 251.4 and 282.8 billion). That is the main reason that automotive sector has been selected for this research.

What is Altman Z-Score Model?

Edward I. Altman, an assistant professor at New York University, published the Z-Score model in 1968. This model is useful for determining whether a company is in financial distress and predicts the likelihood that the company will file for bankruptcy within a given time frame, which is typically two years. Utilising a few control variables from the profit and loss account and balance sheet, it aids the business in gauging its financial health. The Z-score model is really a linear combination of the income statement and balance sheet's five most helpful ratios. To estimate the bankruptcy, Altman weighted the five ratios using the coefficients. It is a discriminant analysis statistical technique. Z-Score Model formula for manufacturing firms is as below:

$$Z = 1.2 X1 + 1.4 X2 + 3.3 X3 + 0.6 X4 + 0.999 X5$$

Where,

$$X1 = \frac{\text{Working Capital}}{\text{Total Assets}}$$

$$X2 = \frac{\text{Retained Earnings}}{\text{Total Assets}}$$

$$X3 = \frac{\text{EBIT}}{\text{Total Assets}}$$

$$X4 = \frac{\text{Market Cap}}{\text{Total Liabilities}}$$

$$X5 = \frac{\text{Revenue}}{\text{Total Assets}}$$

X1: The Working Capital/Total Assets ratio is a measure of the net liquid assets of the firm relative to the total capitalization. Working capital is defined as the difference between current assets and current liabilities. Ordinarily, a firm experiencing consistent operating losses will have shrinking current assets in relation to total assets. Altman found this one proved to be the most valuable liquidity ratio comparing with the current ratio and the quick ratio. This is however the least significant of the five factors.

X2: Retained Earnings/Total Assets: this ratio measures the leverage of a firm. Retained earnings is the account which reports the total amount of reinvested earnings and/or losses of a firm over its entire life. Those firms with high RE, relative to TA, have financed their assets through retention of profits and have not utilized as much debt.

X3, Earnings Before Interest and Taxes/Total Assets: This ratio is a measure of the true productivity of the firm's assets, independent of any tax or leverage factors. Since a firm's ultimate existence is based on the earning power of its assets, this ratio appears to be particularly appropriate for studies dealing with corporate failure. This ratio continually outperforms other profitability measures, including cash flow.

X4, Market Value of Equity/Book Value of Total Liabilities: The measure shows how much the firm's assets can decline in value (measured by market value of equity plus debt) before the liabilities exceed the assets and the firm becomes insolvent.

X5, Revenue/Total Assets: The capital-turnover ratio is a standard financial ratio illustrating the sales generating ability of the firm's assets.

Z Score Decision rule

If Z Score is greater than 2.99	The company is in Safe Zone
If the Z Score is greater than 1.81 but less than 2.99	The company is in Grey Zone
If Z Score is less than 1.81	The company is in Distress Zone

Review of Literature

- **Rohini (2016)** research is based on the model to understand Altman Z score of some selected firms from the BSE and NSE listed companies. The data collection period is for 5 years from 2011-2015. The researcher selects manufacturing and non-manufacturing both the types of companies. The research concludes that none of the companies most of the firms are suffering with the distress zone.
- **Setyani (2016)** the research was based on again Altman Z score and the study period was 2009 to 2014. The Author concludes that the retained earnings to total assets ratio have no significant effect on the company's performance. The other ratio of Z score, EBIT to total assets has the only significant factor which affect the company's stock price but not fully.
- **Sanjaysinh (2020)** The Author has used the Altman Z Score model to analyse the financial distress level of the Havells Company. The Study Period is 10 years from 2009 to 2018. Apart from all the factors of Altman Z Score, the author has also collected the data regarding the ratios like Current Assets ratio, Quick Assets ratio, Debtors Turnover ratio, Liquidity ratio, Return on Assets ratio, Return on Capital Assets ratio etc. On the basis of ten years of Altman Z Score, the research concludes that the Havells company is in Safe Zone in all the ten years.

- **Shivanisinh (2021)** The research study is based on evaluating financial efficiency of selected FMCG companies of India by the Altman z-score model. The study period is five years from 2015 to 2019. The Author has selected the five companies from FMCG sector i.e., Dabur India Ltd., Godrej Consumer Ltd., Marico Ltd., Emami Ltd., and Sheela Foam Ltd. by using convenience sampling method. With the help of Altman Z score, it is being analysed that none of the selected companies are in distress zone.

Objectives of the Study

1. To ascertain the selected automaker companies' financial standing.
2. To assess the degree of hardship experienced by the selected automaker companies.
3. To determine the zone in which the chosen automaker companies are located.
4. To try and use the most widely used performance evaluation methodology to examine the data of the selected automaker companies.

Sample Size and Sampling Procedure

Sample size in NINE selected automaker companies.

The companies are selected by using the judgemental sampling method. The selection has been done on the basis of Market capitalization shown in the BSE and NSE listed companies.

Data Collection

This case study is based on secondary data collection in which data has collected from the IIMA library by using a CMIE data source, other related information is collected from the websites and E-magazines.

Period of the Study

The period of the study will be of TEN years i.e. from 2014 to 2023.

Limitations of the Study

1. Only NINE companies are selected for this research.
2. Companies are selected on judgmental sampling method.
3. Financial distress level evaluation has been done through one model.
4. Data analysis has not been done by using statistical inference.

Data Analysis Tools and Techniques

As the title of this research paper shows, this research study is focusing on selected automaker companies on model of Altman Z Score, the data analysis has been done only by using all the concerning factors of Alman Z Score.

Table No. 1 : Year wise and Factor wise data

Company Name	BS_Year End	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	ALTMAN SCORE	Z
Ashok Leyland Ltd.	202303	0.02 5	0.18 5	0.01 6	1.80 8	0.44 0	1.867	
Ashok Leyland Ltd.	202203	- 0.00 5	0.23 8	0.04 1	1.69 3	0.66 7	2.145	
Ashok Leyland Ltd.	202103	- 0.04 5	0.27 8	0.05 8	1.80 5	1.02 6	2.636	
Ashok Leyland Ltd.	202003	- 0.09 6	0.35 5	0.09 1	0.77 1	1.22 9	2.371	
Ashok Leyland Ltd.	201903	- 0.03 3	0.37 8	0.13 9	1.46 6	1.44 6	3.272	
Ashok Leyland Ltd.	201803	- 0.04 4	0.46 3	0.14 8	2.45 3	1.67 6	4.231	
Ashok Leyland Ltd.	201703	- 0.03 2	0.49 5	0.03 4	1.71 4	1.24 4	3.037	
Ashok Leyland Ltd.	201603	0.02 3	0.52 0	- 0.00 8	2.41 8	1.19 8	3.376	
Ashok Leyland Ltd.	201503	- 0.02 4	0.52 6	0.06 2	1.57 2	1.62 9	3.484	
Ashok Leyland Ltd.	201403	- 0.08 3	0.63 2	0.18 7	0.49 2	2.82 2	4.518	
Ashok Leyland Ltd.	Average	- 0.03 1	0.40 7	0.07 7	1.61 9	1.33 8	3.094	
Bajaj Auto Ltd.	202303	0.11 8	0.29 9	0.14 9	3.61 0	0.64 7	3.865	
Bajaj Auto Ltd.	202203	0.16 6	0.32 6	0.12 8	3.31 1	0.67 7	3.742	

Bajaj Auto Ltd.	202103	0.27 1	0.41 2	0.17 6	3.37 0	0.71 6	4.219
Bajaj Auto Ltd.	202003	0.09 5	0.67 6	0.21 5	2.36 5	0.87 9	4.068
Bajaj Auto Ltd.	201903	0.08 0	0.68 7	0.21 1	3.08 1	0.92 1	4.524
Bajaj Auto Ltd.	201803	0.21 5	0.90 2	0.28 2	3.33 9	1.27 4	5.727
Bajaj Auto Ltd.	201703	0.29 7	0.94 3	0.31 6	3.90 3	1.43 7	6.498
Bajaj Auto Ltd.	201603	0.11 8	1.51 0	0.36 1	4.22 3	1.68 3	7.661
Bajaj Auto Ltd.	201503	0.32 4	1.69 3	0.41 9	3.75 1	2.13 0	8.519
Bajaj Auto Ltd.	201403	0.06 0	1.70 1	0.50 5	3.98 8	2.47 0	8.980
Bajaj Auto Ltd.	Average	0.17 4	0.91 5	0.27 6	3.49 4	1.28 3	5.780
Eicher Motors Ltd.	202303	0.02 7	0.07 1	0.04 7	4.78 0	0.18 0	3.336
Eicher Motors Ltd.	202203	0.19 1	0.16 1	0.13 0	4.73 0	0.43 5	4.156
Eicher Motors Ltd.	202103	0.50 0	0.30 5	0.18 1	5.63 7	0.55 7	5.563
Eicher Motors Ltd.	202003	0.42 4	0.50 0	0.25 1	0.33 8	0.84 7	3.083
Eicher Motors Ltd.	201903	0.25 4	0.74 3	0.33 1	0.59 1	1.03 3	3.824
Eicher Motors Ltd.	201803	0.04 2	1.04 9	0.31 3	0.99 1	1.16 5	4.311
Eicher Motors Ltd.	201703	- 0.02 2	1.73 2	0.32 4	1.25 5	1.55 6	5.774
Eicher Motors Ltd.	201603	- 0.03 4	2.37 4	0.47 0	1.15 1	2.24 1	7.763
Eicher Motors Ltd.	201412	0.12 2	5.74 3	1.58 0	1.93 2	6.31 1	20.865
Eicher Motors Ltd.	Average	0.16 7	1.40 9	0.40 3	2.37 8	1.59 2	6.519

Escorts Kubota Ltd.	202303	0.30 7	0.16 6	0.03 7	2.47 5	0.61 0	2.818
Escorts Kubota Ltd.	202203	0.58 1	0.17 9	0.01 3	2.38 1	0.42 5	2.845
Escorts Kubota Ltd.	202103	0.40 4	0.23 8	0.01 9	2.36 1	0.48 2	2.778
Escorts Kubota Ltd.	202003	0.21 1	0.35 2	0.04 7	1.53 0	0.78 1	2.598
Escorts Kubota Ltd.	201903	0.16 5	0.48 5	0.10 8	1.95 5	1.00 0	3.404
Escorts Kubota Ltd.	201803	0.10 7	0.67 8	0.17 3	2.34 9	1.45 1	4.509
Escorts Kubota Ltd.	201703	0.00 0	0.96 7	0.18 9	1.90 6	1.66 2	4.780
Escorts Kubota Ltd.	201603	- 0.03 7	1.62 3	0.36 2	0.52 8	2.14 7	5.884
Escorts Kubota Ltd.	201503	- 0.01 2	2.31 5	0.31 0	0.45 4	2.15 5	6.676
Escorts Kubota Ltd.	201403	0.01 1	2.37 9	0.23 4	0.39 4	2.39 4	6.744
Escorts Kubota Ltd.	Average	0.17 4	0.93 8	0.14 9	1.63 3	1.31 1	4.304
Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	202303	0.14 1	0.23 0	0.11 9	1.93 8	1.04 4	3.090
Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	202203	0.22 4	0.28 9	0.14 8	2.03 9	1.22 5	3.610
Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	202103	0.21 0	0.38 1	0.19 2	2.52 3	1.23 2	4.165
Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	202003	0.21 8	0.50 8	0.23 5	1.60 6	1.43 8	4.149
Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	201903	0.20 7	0.60 9	0.27 3	2.65 4	1.67 6	5.269
Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	201803	0.24 8	0.70 4	0.27 6	3.89 4	1.85 0	6.379
Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	201703	0.21 3	0.89 3	0.29 1	4.08 1	1.82 8	6.741
Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	201603	0.20 0	1.11 9	0.29 0	4.34 3	2.27 6	7.641

Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	201503	0.13 4	1.50 4	0.31 4	5.05 1	2.79 9	9.128
Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	201403	0.11 3	1.66 4	0.39 0	4.54 3	3.38 4	9.858
Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	Average	0.19 1	0.79 0	0.25 3	3.26 7	1.87 5	6.003
Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	202303	0.10 7	0.21 6	0.06 1	1.83 2	0.53 5	2.265
Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	202203	0.10 8	0.28 3	0.06 6	1.44 8	0.57 7	2.188
Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	202103	0.07 5	0.35 7	0.07 3	1.54 3	0.66 4	2.419
Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	202003	0.08 3	0.52 0	0.09 8	0.67 3	0.87 2	2.425
Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	201903	0.07 3	0.55 9	0.12 0	1.51 9	0.92 4	3.100
Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	201803	0.06 4	0.70 4	0.13 8	1.85 6	1.13 0	3.759
Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	201703	0.07 5	0.84 6	0.08 4	0.96 0	1.14 5	3.271
Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	201603	0.05 0	0.96 1	0.08 3	1.00 8	1.25 7	3.540
Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	201503	0.03 5	1.13 4	0.20 2	1.06 6	1.75 4	4.690
Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	201403	0.08 1	1.35 8	0.27 4	0.92 5	2.71 5	6.172
Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	Average	0.07 5	0.69 4	0.12 0	1.28 3	1.15 7	3.383
Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	202303	- 0.10 3	0.25 1	0.04 6	3.02 4	0.52 9	2.724
Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	202203	- 0.00 3	0.32 2	0.06 9	3.12 0	0.68 3	3.230
Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	202103	0.02 7	0.42 4	0.10 7	2.95 3	0.82 0	3.571
Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	202003	- 0.04 6	0.58 0	0.16 1	2.07 1	1.08 8	3.616

Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	201903	- 0.02 8	0.66 1	0.18 0	3.20 2	1.26 7	4.674
Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	201803	- 0.12 7	0.77 5	0.17 8	4.51 0	1.44 9	5.672
Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	201703	- 0.08 7	0.94 2	0.14 0	3.55 1	1.47 5	5.283
Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	201603	- 0.07 6	1.22 1	0.12 5	2.67 9	1.67 7	5.315
Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	201503	- 0.01 5	1.26 7	0.11 1	2.62 5	2.07 4	5.769
Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	201403	0.15 7	1.56 4	0.26 9	1.54 7	3.05 2	7.242
Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	Average	- 0.03 0	0.80 1	0.13 9	2.92 8	1.41 1	4.709
Tata Motors Ltd.	202303	- 0.23 7	0.30 7	0.00 5	2.67 2	0.56 9	2.335
Tata Motors Ltd.	202203	- 0.17 8	0.22 3	- 0.03 7	2.59 8	0.56 8	2.102
Tata Motors Ltd.	202103	- 0.16 3	0.34 7	0.02 3	1.77 6	0.65 9	2.091
Tata Motors Ltd.	202003	- 0.19 9	0.32 7	- 0.01 3	0.40 8	0.70 8	1.131
Tata Motors Ltd.	201903	- 0.16 2	0.32 0	0.01 3	0.97 2	0.95 1	1.829
Tata Motors Ltd.	201803	- 0.16 0	0.36 3	0.07 1	1.87 8	1.16 9	2.844

Tata Motors Ltd.	201703	- 0.14 9	0.28 5	- 0.08 8	2.68 7	0.74 6	2.289
Tata Motors Ltd.	201603	- 0.12 1	0.32 2	- 0.00 3	2.31 4	0.53 2	2.217
Tata Motors Ltd.	201503	- 0.23 6	0.38 3	0.01 0	3.50 7	0.94 6	3.334
Tata Motors Ltd.	201403	- 0.24 2	0.43 5	0.06 6	2.55 1	1.32 2	3.389
Tata Motors Ltd.	Average	- 0.18 5	0.33 1	0.00 5	2.13 6	0.81 7	2.356
TVS Motor Company Ltd.	202303	- 0.16 7	0.09 8	0.02 7	3.65 8	0.56 9	2.789
TVS Motor Company Ltd.	202203	- 0.15 5	0.13 4	0.04 1	2.49 7	0.84 4	2.478
TVS Motor Company Ltd.	202103	- 0.11 2	0.18 7	0.06 6	2.72 6	1.08 9	3.071
TVS Motor Company Ltd.	202003	- 0.13 6	0.25 2	0.07 9	1.50 8	1.29 7	2.653
TVS Motor Company Ltd.	201903	- 0.10 6	0.33 8	0.11 2	2.69 3	1.81 3	4.143
TVS Motor Company Ltd.	201803	- 0.17 1	0.46 1	0.14 6	4.09 6	2.54 5	5.920
TVS Motor Company Ltd.	201703	- 0.11 2	0.60 5	0.14 5	3.47 3	2.78 1	6.053
TVS Motor Company Ltd.	201603	- 0.08 7	0.83 3	0.19 5	3.09 5	3.38 2	6.943

TVS Motor Company Ltd.	201503	- 0.04 7	1.03 7	0.29 1	2.72 1	4.51 5	8.499
TVS Motor Company Ltd.	201403	- 0.03 4	1.68 3	0.60 1	1.29 8	7.40 0	12.472
TVS Motor Company Ltd.	Average	- 0.11 3	0.56 3	0.17 0	2.77 7	2.62 4	5.502

Interpretation: The above table shows that the entire data of all the factors of altman z score from the year march 2014 to march 2023. The data shown in pink background is an average of all the ten years. Last column shows that the altman z score of each year and altman z score on average basis. Lowest altman z score is detected in tata motors for the year of 2020 while highest altman z score is detected in Eicher motors for the year of 2014.

Table No.2: Yearly Altman Z Score of selected automobile companies

BS_Year End	Ashok Leyland Ltd.	Bajaj Auto Ltd.	Eicher Motors Ltd.	Escorts Kubota Ltd.	Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	Tata Motors Ltd.	TVS Motor Company Ltd.
Mar_2023	1.867	3.865	3.336	2.818	3.090	2.265	2.724	2.335	2.789
Mar_2022	2.145	3.742	4.156	2.845	3.610	2.188	3.230	2.102	2.478
Mar_2021	2.636	4.219	5.563	2.778	4.165	2.419	3.571	2.091	3.071
Mar_2020	2.371	4.068	3.083	2.598	4.149	2.425	3.616	1.131	2.653
Mar_2019	3.272	4.524	3.824	3.404	5.269	3.100	4.674	1.829	4.143
Mar_2018	4.231	5.727	4.311	4.509	6.379	3.759	5.672	2.844	5.920
Mar_2017	3.037	6.498	5.774	4.780	6.741	3.271	5.283	2.289	6.053
Mar_2016	3.376	7.661	7.763	5.884	7.641	3.540	5.315	2.217	6.943

Mar_2015	3.484	8.519	20.865	6.676	9.128	4.690	5.769	3.334	8.499
Mar_2014	4.518	8.980		6.744	9.858	6.172	7.242	3.389	12.472

Interpretation: the above table shows the data of altman z score of all the selected automobile companies for all the 10 years. In this table the lowest altman z score is detected in tata motors for the year of 2020 while highest altman z score is detected in Eicher motors for the year of 2014. According to the z score decision rule, out of 90 altman z score, the only one altman z score is detected less than 1.81. which means the company is in distress zone. While The company is in Grey Zone where Z Score is greater than 1.81 but less than 2.99 are 23 scores. but the noticeable thing is that Bajaj Auto, Eicher motors and Hero motocorp companies are exceptionally good that in ten years' time duration they never came into either in distress zone or in grey zone. And the good part of this research is that there are 65 altman z scores from 90 scores are in safe zone which is a 72.22% of the entire data analysis.

Table No. 3: Factor-wise Analysis of selected automobile companies

Sr.No	Company Name	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	Altman Z Score
1	Ashok Leyland Ltd.	-0.031	0.407	0.077	1.619	1.338	3.094
2	Bajaj Auto Ltd.	0.174	0.915	0.276	3.494	1.283	5.780
3	Eicher Motors Ltd.	0.167	1.409	0.403	2.378	1.592	6.519
4	Escorts Kubota Ltd.	0.174	0.938	0.149	1.633	1.311	4.304
5	Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	0.191	0.790	0.253	3.267	1.875	6.003
6	Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	0.075	0.694	0.120	1.283	1.157	3.383
7	Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	-0.030	0.801	0.139	2.928	1.411	4.709
8	Tata Motors Ltd.	-0.185	0.331	0.005	2.136	0.817	2.356
9	TVS Motor Company Ltd.	-0.113	0.563	0.170	2.777	2.624	5.502

Interpretation: According to 'Z' Score Decision rule, if 'Z' Score is less than 1.81, the company is in distress zone and the companies below 2.99 z score is in grey zone. Factor-wise Analysis shows that the only Altman Z-score of Tata Motors Ltd. shows their position in grey zone while all the other companies on an average show they are in safe zone as far as the altman z score model analysis is concerned. This implies that the bankruptcy possibilities is not been seen in any of the selected automobile companies.

Chart No. 1: Factor wise Comparison

Chart : 2 - Altman Z Score from the Average of Ten Years

Chart 3: Year Wise Trend Analysis of Selected Automobile Cos.

Findings

Factor	Lowest	Year	Highest	Year
X1	Tata Motors Ltd.	2014	Escorts Kubota Ltd.	2022
X2	Eicher Motors Ltd.	2023	Eicher Motors Ltd.	2014
X3	Tata Motors Ltd.	2017	Eicher Motors Ltd.	2014
X4	Eicher Motors Ltd.	2020	Eicher Motors Ltd.	2021
X5	Eicher Motors Ltd.	2023	TVS Motors Ltd.	2014

- As far as the factor of alman z score is concerned eicher motors have shown more fluctuation in lowest performed companies as well as highest performed companies.

- Out of the selected nine companies of 10 years data, only 1.11% of altman z score is in distress zone.
- Tata motors is the only company which shows distress level out of the selected nine companies but it is only for one accounting year.
- 25% of altman z score data are in grey zone.
- While 72.22% altman z scores are in safe zone of selected automobile companies.
- Three companies - Bajaj Auto, Eicher motors and Hero motocorp companies are shown exceptionally good altman z score that in ten years' time duration they never came into either in distress zone or in grey zone.

Conclusion

The data analysis concludes that the selected nine automobile companies are exceptionally good in altman z score data as overall 99% of altman z scores are not in distress level. Only one company i.e. tata motors ltd. have shown altman z score in grey zone on an average of 10 years of data. Out of the sample selected 33.33% companies have never faced even a minor distress level in terms of financial as far as altman z score is concerned. The only doubtful situation have been seen in Eicher motors that the company has lowest altman z score in 2014 and suddenly after one year it has shown the highest alman z score in 2015. However, altman z score implies a bankruptcy possibility for two years, no companies from the selected automobile companies have been seen the bankruptcy possibilities.

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Annexure

Company Name	BS_Year End	Working Capital	BS_Total Assets	FH_Reserves and Surplus	FH_PB IT	Mkt Cap.	PL_Net Sales
Ashok Leyland Ltd.	202303	569.77	22591.63	4181.82	361.71	40,848	9943.43
Ashok Leyland Ltd.	202203	-92	20333.78	4834.11	835.7	34,419	13562.18
Ashok Leyland Ltd.	202103	-822.31	18449.91	5122.56	1074.18	33,304	18937.3
Ashok Leyland Ltd.	202003	-1575.44	16389.61	5815.3	1485.46	12,637	20140.13
Ashok Leyland Ltd.	201903	-602.62	18224.4	6884.04	2533.11	26,724	26356.4
Ashok Leyland Ltd.	201803	-756.03	17336.39	8031.75	2567.18	42,531	29054.95
Ashok Leyland Ltd.	201703	-444.48	14040.07	6947.25	471.37	24,062	17467.47
Ashok Leyland Ltd.	201603	290.77	12773.75	6641.44	-105.12	30,892	15301.45
Ashok Leyland Ltd.	201503	-324.22	13311.49	7005.45	828.72	20,931	21688.29
Ashok Leyland Ltd.	201403	-1059.86	12808	8094.32	2399.49	6,306	36144.14
Bajaj Auto Ltd.	202303	3672.37	31127.69	9318.65	4632.54	1,12,386	20149.51
Bajaj Auto Ltd.	202203	5305.03	31921.94	10402.78	4091.28	1,05,691	21612.01
Bajaj Auto Ltd.	202103	8531.92	31530.2	12977.18	5548.37	1,06,247	22586.52
Bajaj Auto Ltd.	202003	2343.75	24773.3	16744.76	5337.03	58,594	21766.68
Bajaj Auto Ltd.	201903	2188.98	27380.39	18814.49	5783.88	84,352	25218.92

Bajaj Auto Ltd.	20180 3	5124.3 4	23819. 49	21490.53	6707.64	79,544	30357. 57
Bajaj Auto Ltd.	20170 3	6178.7 9	20814. 89	19626.11	6583.36	81,240	29918. 65
Bajaj Auto Ltd.	20160 3	1944.2 6	16486. 5	24895.98	5945.66	69,625	27741. 08
Bajaj Auto Ltd.	20150 3	5049.4 8	15562. 32	26347.16	6513.99	58,375	33144. 71
Bajaj Auto Ltd.	20140 3	886.39	14747. 6	25080.81	7448.12	58,807	36427. 6
Eicher Motors Ltd.	20230 3	454.84	16875. 5	1206.56	799.7	80,664	3031.2 2
Eicher Motors Ltd.	20220 3	2709.5 1	14222. 8	2284.02	1855.13	67,274	6186.1 9
Eicher Motors Ltd.	20210 3	6316.4 8	12624. 91	3850.25	2279.78	71,170	7037.9 7
Eicher Motors Ltd.	20200 3	4481.4 7	10579. 01	5285.17	2651.31	3,573	8957.5 1
Eicher Motors Ltd.	20190 3	2406.1 9	9477.4 1	7040.42	3135.97	5,603	9794.4 8
Eicher Motors Ltd.	20180 3	329.79	7794.6 7	8178.05	2441.2	7,723	9077.4 7
Eicher Motors Ltd.	20170 3	-121.6	5540.2 6	9597.8	1792.51	6,953	8619.0 4
Eicher Motors Ltd.	20160 3	-152.15	4517.5 4	10726.27	2122.32	5,199	10122. 86
Eicher Motors Ltd.	20141 2	271.83	2228.8 9	12801.24	3521.29	4,307	14066. 64
Escorts Kubota Ltd.	20230 3	3163.2 7	10308. 13	1711.78	383.07	25,509	6291.5 1
Escorts Kubota Ltd.	20220 3	5443.7 7	9371.7 4	1676.97	125.36	22,316	3985.8 3
Escorts Kubota Ltd.	20210 3	2907.1 4	7203.2 3	1715.03	136.8	17,005	3469.1 8
Escorts Kubota Ltd.	20200 3	1120.6 4	5312.0 8	1868.48	249.4	8,126	4147.0 7
Escorts Kubota Ltd.	20190 3	825.47	4996.9 4	2425.53	537.39	9,768	4995.1 2
Escorts Kubota Ltd.	20180 3	456.31	4269.4 9	2896.25	739.68	10,031	6196.3 6
Escorts Kubota Ltd.	20170 3	0.91	3466.1 1	3350.4	654.3	6,606	5760.9 5
Escorts Kubota Ltd.	20160 3	-119.88	3227.4	5237.58	1168.09	1,704	6929.2 9
Escorts Kubota Ltd.	20150 3	-38.8	3339.2 8	7732.08	1034.58	1,515	7196.9

Escorts Kubota Ltd.	201403	39.02	3485.33	8290.57	815.39	1,373	8344.95
Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	202303	3412.81	24201.89	5559.93	2879.07	46,905	25275.47
Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	202203	5042.58	22510.1	6500.72	3339.91	45,893	27585.3
Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	202103	4842.57	23078.89	8793.18	4439.76	58,239	28442.7
Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	202003	4312.5	19822.75	10067.45	4664.51	31,842	28500.46
Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	201903	3985.28	19232.64	11722.2	5250.41	51,035	32230.49
Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	201803	4504.86	18185.75	12807.58	5019.33	70,808	33650.54
Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	201703	3359.85	15776.34	14081.01	4595.71	64,384	28836.09
Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	201603	2702.9	13533.74	15139.43	3922.22	58,777	30800.62
Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	201503	1398.71	10448.16	15718.51	3275.93	52,769	29245.47
Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	201403	1132.88	9991.32	16629.49	3894.43	45,386	33805.65
Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	202303	8096.15	75779.81	16357.33	4628.65	1,38,808	40508.5
Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	202203	7194.76	66606.5	18852.8	4383.19	96,422	38444.83
Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	202103	4624.72	61564.49	21989.35	4470.51	94,996	40875.07
Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	202003	4168.67	50502.06	26271.98	4926.68	34,002	44053.5
Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	201903	3852.58	52697.06	29469.74	6308.03	80,051	48685.55
Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	201803	3041.16	47446.7	33379.51	6534.38	88,079	53614
Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	201703	2973.95	39713.48	33606.36	3325.16	38,131	45487.78
Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	201603	1791.36	35499.57	34098.73	2947.52	35,769	44629.87
Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	201503	1153.94	32944.87	37368.77	6668.1	35,104	57786.94
Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	201403	2522.13	31288.65	42497.35	8586.05	28,945	84960.26
Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	202303	-8499.4	82837.6	20827	3834.4	2,50,504	43791.8
Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	202203	-232.5	73191.6	23553.2	5074.2	2,28,370	49970.6

Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	202103	1880.4	70160.8	29733.2	7525.2	2,07,219	57538.1
Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	202003	-2867.4	62552.1	36280.1	10049.7	1,29,524	68034.8
Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	201903	-1788.7	62931.8	41606.3	11349.1	2,01,539	79762.7
Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	201803	-7520.7	59370.1	45990.5	10541.4	2,67,738	86020.3
Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	201703	-4450.2	51250.6	48286	7197.7	1,81,982	75610.6
Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	201603	-3193.2	41940	51215.8	5260.2	1,12,347	70332.5
Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	201503	-625.1	42567.2	53935	4708.2	1,11,747	88295.6
Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	201403	6053.3	38506.5	60231	10345.7	59,552	117522.9
Tata Motors Ltd.	202303	-14303.58	60293.51	18532.87	327.38	1,61,083	34288.11
Tata Motors Ltd.	202203	-11373.2	63899.87	14218.81	-2363.04	1,65,994	36301.63
Tata Motors Ltd.	202103	-10617.76	65059.66	22582.93	1524.9	1,15,573	42845.47
Tata Motors Ltd.	202003	-12433.13	62589.87	20483.39	-784.26	25,560	44316.34
Tata Motors Ltd.	201903	-9873.75	60909.63	19491.76	797.51	59,190	57896.53
Tata Motors Ltd.	201803	-9470.62	59212.3	21474.86	4192.5	1,11,197	69202.76
Tata Motors Ltd.	201703	-8781.27	58878.28	16787.47	-5154.34	1,58,230	43928.17
Tata Motors Ltd.	201603	-6840.05	56676	18267.98	-163.89	1,31,175	30175.03
Tata Motors Ltd.	201503	-11797.66	49943.17	19133.61	481.68	1,75,138	47263.68
Tata Motors Ltd.	201403	-12058.47	49734.42	21639.88	3302.31	1,26,858	65757.33

TVS Company Ltd.	Motor	20230 3	- 2341.0 4	13992. 39	1367.77	377.94	51,186	7965.9 4
TVS Company Ltd.	Motor	20220 3	- 1839.2 5	11902. 31	1597.85	485.36	29,724	10042. 33
TVS Company Ltd.	Motor	20210 3	- 1138.6 2	10197. 45	1910.83	677.67	27,797	11104. 66
TVS Company Ltd.	Motor	20200 3	- 1272.5 7	9353.3 2	2360.82	742.63	14,105	12135. 31
TVS Company Ltd.	Motor	20190 3	-886.77	8369.3 6	2832.91	935.26	22,541	15175. 41
TVS Company Ltd.	Motor	20180 3	-1226.3	7156.2 4	3299.81	1041.52	29,310	18209. 92
TVS Company Ltd.	Motor	20170 3	-664.19	5904.6 7	3570.58	856.6	20,505	16423. 34
TVS Company Ltd.	Motor	20160 3	-429.51	4952.1 8	4123.44	967.84	15,329	16750. 54
TVS Company Ltd.	Motor	20150 3	-214.36	4604.6 5	4774.53	1339.13	12,530	20790. 51
TVS Company Ltd.	Motor	20140 3	-120.44	3564.7	6000.34	2144.03	4,627	26378. 09